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Characterisation of heterogeneous permeability in LCM processes using stochastic inversion and neural surrogates

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“Conventional” permeability testing (as in ISO 4410)

- Flow experiments
- Simple geometries
- Uses analytical solution for relation between flow velocity and pressure gradient
- Results in one permeability value or a set of principal permeability values at a nominal fibre volume fraction
- Does not really work if there are local variations in permeability or edge effects (racetracking)

Idea

Recover local distributions of fibre volume fraction and permeability in specimens with non-uniform properties in real time; potentially in the presence of racetracking.

Domain for flow analysis

- 300 mm × 300 mm
- linear inlet and vent
- constant pressure difference
- constant viscosity

Partitioning of domain

$$9 \times 9 + 2 \times 2 \text{ (racetracking)}$$

➔ 85 unknown values of permeability and porosity

Virtual pressure sensors

- record pressure as a function of time
- for all sensors
 - or for subsets

Method: Inversion

(Unknown) true distribution of permeability and porosity

experiment

Recorded pressure-time curves

Recover local properties

Ensemble of J samples

Mean

CVFEM simulations

Results from all J samples

First guess ("prior")

Not a good match with recorded data

Update ensemble

Method: Inversion

(Unknown) true distribution of permeability and porosity

experiment

Recorded pressure-time curves

Recover local properties

Ensemble of J samples

updated

Mean

CVFEM simulations

Results from all J samples

Improved, but still not a good match

Update ensemble

Method: Inversion

(Unknown) true distribution of permeability and porosity

experiment

Recorded pressure-time curves

Recover local properties

Ensemble of J samples

updated

Mean

CVFEM simulations

Results from all J samples

Acceptable match

Ensemble is "posterior" approximation

Run time for each CVFEM simulation ~ 100 s

Simulations for thousands of samples required.

➔ Even with parallel computing, finding posterior approximation takes hours.

To speed up inversion:

Generate a data set based on CVFEM simulation for 50,000 samples, all with different properties.

Use Artificial Neural Network as surrogate to interpolate outputs for unseen parameter sets, near-instantaneously.

Wells, H., Park, M., Matveev, M., & Tretyakov, M. (2024). RTM-Flow: Control volume FEM solver for 2D moving boundary problems (v2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12583662>

Method: Surrogate

85 values of

- permeability
- porosity

Injection pressure
Viscosity

Pressure values

- all sensors
- 14 observation times

Red: CVFEM simulation
Black: Neural network prediction
Grey: surrogate uncertainty

	Relative error (average)	Execution time (average)
CVFEM	-	109 s
Surrogate	1.15 %	3.52×10^{-4} s

“Truth”

Log-permeability

Observed flow front shapes and recovered local permeability and porosity.

Porosity

Increasing levels of detail are recovered as the flow front propagates.

Permeability and porosity

- recovered at end of impregnation process;
- averaged on sub-domains identified as “background”, “inclusions” and “racetracking channels”.

	background		inclusions		racetracking channels	
	K / m^2	Φ	K / m^2	Φ	K / m^2	Φ
“truth”	4.50×10^{-10}	0.66	2.05×10^{-10}	0.40	2.50×10^{-8}	0.98
recovered	4.65×10^{-10}	0.64	2.18×10^{-10}	0.45	2.39×10^{-8}	0.98
Δ	+ 3 %	- 3 %	+ 6 %	+ 12 %	- 4 %	± 0 %

Quantitatively, porosity and permeability can be recovered with acceptable accuracy.

Virtual experiments: Results

Number of sensors considered in inversion

Log-permeability

“Truth”

ensemble mean

standard deviation

Uncertainty in recovered permeability decreases with increasing number of sensors.

Lab experiments: Set-up

Reinforcement:
Random glass fibre mat;
 $S_0 = (210 \pm 15) \text{ g/m}^2$

Example lay-up:

- 7 layers (background)
- 10 layers, 80 mm diameter (inclusion)

Test fluid:

Synthetic engine oil; $\eta \approx 0.1 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$

Pressure difference:

$\Delta p \approx 10^5 \text{ Pa}$

- 300 mm \times 300 mm, 2.1 mm height
- 23 pressure sensors
- transparent lid for flow front tracking

Recovery of porosity and permeability as flow front propagates

Visual flow front tracking

Log-permeability

Porosity

Note: 19 sensors considered here (2x2 omitted)

Permeability and porosity

Comparison with results from “conventional” permeability testing (uniform, at comparable number of layers, n , and cavity height, h)

	background		inclusion	
	K / m^2	Φ	K / m^2	Φ
conv.	6.29×10^{-10}	0.73	3.77×10^{-10}	0.61
recovered	5.86×10^{-10}	0.72	3.34×10^{-10}	0.57
Δ	- 7 %	- 1 %	- 11 %	- 8 %

$$\Phi = 1 - \frac{n S_0}{\rho h}$$

K interpolated at Φ
based on “conventional”
test series

Quantitatively, recovered porosity and permeability are reasonably consistent with results from “conventional” testing.

Note: Results from “conventional” testing are affected by uncertainty as well.

An Artificial Neural Network surrogate was combined with a stochastic inversion algorithm to estimate local reinforcement permeability and porosity in real time based on in-process data.

Virtual and lab experiments indicate that

- positions and shape of inclusions and racetracking channels can be identified correctly;
- recovered values of permeability and porosity are generally in good agreement with the corresponding “true” values.

As the reinforcement properties can be recovered in real time, integration of this algorithm within active process control systems is feasible.

Recover local permeabilities for more complex geometries

Example: “stiffened panel”

complex overlap configuration
+ noodle regions
+ racetracking

4 inlets, 5 vents

20 pressure sensors,
visual monitoring on flat side

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